

BIOLOGY AND GROWTH TECHNOLOGY OF THE HAIR PLANT. BLOOD RED HAIR

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The direction of technology of cultivation and processing of medicinal plants
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6390213>

Abstract: This article provides information on the biology of hawthorn, its distribution, species, importance in folk medicine, chemical composition, treatment of diseases, as well as information on tinctures and tinctures that can be used in diseases.

Keywords: Distribution of hawthorn, crataegur L, species, many diseases, functional disorders of the heart, hypertension, angina pectoris, antigioneuroses, atrial fibrillation, paraxysmal tachycardia, general atherosclerosis, for climacteric neuroses, drops, decoctions, decoctions, , Blood red (CRATAEGUS SANGUINEA PALL), fat, sugar, vitamin C,

Medicinal plants, which are distributed in all regions of the country and are considered medical treasures, are a source of benefits for human health. That is why the attention to medicinal plants distributed in the country is growing day by day. On measures to expand the scope of scientific research on the development of cultivation and processing, the establishment of their single seed "Appendix PQ-4901 November 26, 2020 1. According to him, the creation of a single base of scientific research on the cultivation and processing of medicinal plants in the country, the study of advanced scientific developments of foreign countries, the study of cooperation with leading scientific institutions and the introduction of modern technologies, scientific developments in the country and future work, such as the efficient use of available resources. PQ-4670 was established for implementation on April 10, 2020. is coming. In other words, out of more than 4.3 thousand plants belonging to the local flora, 750 species are medicinal plants, 112 species of which are registered for use in scientific medicine, of which 70 species are actively used in the pharmaceutical industry.

In addition, we all know that our country has a long tradition of treating various diseases on the basis of medicinal plants. Because our ancestors knew the properties of medicinal plants and were able to use them effectively. It is no secret that almost all diseases are cured by drugs. It is no coincidence that today

in all regions of the country, the forest fund and medicinal plants are grown. Therefore, in the irrigated areas and arable lands of the republic, training of personnel for the cultivation of medicinal plants and their plantations is underway.

The number of medicinal plants in the territory of the republic is very high, they have annual forms such as annual, biennial, perennial, shrub, semi-shrub and tree. Plants with a living form of a shrub or tree can be harvested for many years. For example, the hawthorn plant has medicinal properties and is used for consumption.

Biology of the hawthorn plant: The hawthorn (*Crataegus* L) is a tree or shrub belonging to the family Hawthorn. The body is 6-10 meters high and 40-50 cm thick. There are 890 species, 10 of which grow in Uzbekistan. They are also found in China, Spain, Italy, Algeria, the United States and other countries. The edges of the leaves are large toothed or pinnate. Arranged in rows at the base. The flower is small, clustered in an inflorescence. Fruits are 1-5 grains. There are varieties of hawthorn, which are grown as an ornamental plant, as well as hawthorn, yellow hawthorn, red hawthorn. In the regions and districts at altitudes of 1000-1500 meters above sea level, it often grows alone, sometimes small hawthorn. Hawthorn plants are also found in the form of small gardens. The fruits of some species are large, widely consumed. . The flowers of the yellow hawthorn are very rich in nectar. The hawthorn plant blooms in May-June. It ripens in late September. The total yield of the 25-30-year-old tree is 70-80 kg on average. , Contains 5-15.9% sugar, 8% fat, 0.67-0.88% malic acid .It is one of the most valuable medicinal plants in folk medicine due to the presence of these biologically active substances. Decoction of hawthorn bark, leaves, and roots is also a means of coloring various fabrics. In this case, the fabric turns the fabric yellow-brown. It can be a good grafting tag for apples, pears, and quinces. Yellow hawthorn (*CRATEAGUS PONTICA* L) is common in most parts of Uzbekistan. This type of hawthorn is consumed by the people. In medicine, the fruits and flowers of 6 species of hawthorn are allowed. The most common is red hawthorn (*CRATEAGUS TURKESTANIICA*).

Chemical composition: The fruit of the hawthorn plant contains 20% sugar, 8% fat, flavanoids, choline, acetylcholine, additives, carotene, vitamin C, organic acids, kratogin, substances. In addition to the above substances, the flowers of the plant contain about 0.16% of essential oil. That is why in folk medicine The

lana plant is used in hallucinations (inability to concentrate), insomnia, heart attacks.

Medicinal properties of hawthorn plant in folk medicine The medicinal properties of hawthorn plant have been known since ancient times. Ibn Sina used hawthorn fruit as a means of stopping diarrhea. The fruits of the hawthorn plant are considered to be medicinal. The great physician Ibn Sina recommended infusions and decoctions made from the fruit of the great doctor Ibn Sina as a laxative for diarrhea. Alcohol tincture and extract of hawthorn is recommended by doctors for patients with angioneurosis (vascular neurosis, functional disorders of the blood vessels), cardiac dysfunction, increased blood pressure, heart failure in patients with infectious diseases, inflammation of the palate. 'lana is part of cardiovalen preporat. Prepare from the fruit The drugs improve the contraction of the heart muscle, reduce cholesterol in the blood from its irritation. It is said that hawthorn preparations also improve the function of the mammary glands (GUSEYNOV 1961). Hawthorn is mainly used in the treatment of functional disorders of the heart, hypertension, angina pectoris, antigioneurosis, atrial fibrillation, parasympathetic tachycardia, general atherosclerosis, climacteric neurosis. It is also used in the treatment of thyroid disease.

For the preparation of drugs: For the preparation of medicinal products from hawthorn berries in the autumn when the fruits ripen, they are also separated from foreign compounds and dried. Lana fruit can be boiled at home. In this case, we add 20 grams of hawthorn berries to a teapot or pot, boil 200 grams of boiling water over a low flame for 15 minutes. Boiled juice can also be consumed instead of tea.

The hawthorn plant and its preparations should not be consumed on an empty stomach. Because it squeezes the gut and makes people vomit. Also, do not drink cold water after consuming this plant. This is because of the fact that the stomach can cause colic. So there are a number of guidelines for eating the fruit. Excessive consumption of fruit can lead to impaired kidney function. Neglected hawthorn berries and drugs can cause gastrointestinal weakness, colitis, nausea and vomiting. Also, hawthorn decoctions, tinctures, syrups and medicines made from them should be consumed on the advice of a doctor, and we should be under medical supervision when consuming.

Meeting in Uzbekistan: According to natural scientists, more than 326,800 hawthorn plants are grown on 1214 hectares in Burchmulla and Chirchik

forests in the Bostanlyk zone of the Tashkent region of the republic. If the fruit is soaked or rotten, the skin of the hop can be picked up to 30-40 days.

Hawthorn cultivation technology: Hawthorn fruits ripen fully and normally in September. The seeds are rubbed on the flesh of the fruit, washed in water and separated from the flesh. unigan plants. That is, it takes a long time for the seeds to bear fruit when they are sown. But it is difficult to grow such seedlings. This requires the following agricultural techniques. To reproduce the hawthorn plant from seeds, fully ripe seeds are selected. These ripe fruits are separated from the rest and peeled. Once the seeds have been separated, they should be stripped. Stripped seeds should be sown in late autumn. Seeds should be mulched before sowing and it is advisable to keep them moist after sowing. If you have to use last year's seeds to grow seedlings, sow them in June-July. The norm for yellow hawthorn seeds is 25-30 g / m, for ordinary hawthorn 15-18 g / m, sowing depth is 4 cm. Hawthorn seeds germinate within 6-8 months after sowing. After germination, hawthorn seedlings are cared for in accordance with the agro-ecological requirements of forestry. After germination, they are transplanted to a permanent place after 1-2 years. Hawthorn seedlings are planted 5-6 years after planting. kata tree, enters the ranks of the bushes and gradually begins to bear fruit.

There is no special requirement for growing hawthorn seedlings. Like other plants, it is planted, watered and fertilized. Hawthorn seedlings are harvested in 4-5 years after planting.

Healing of red hawthorn

Blood-red hawthorn (*CRATAEGUS SANGUINEA* PALL) Common hawthorn is a blood-red shrub, rarely a member of the ROSACEAE family, up to 5 m tall, sometimes 10-12 m tall. bekamikost shear. The petiole has a short petiolate base and a large toothed edge, dark green in summer and orange-red in autumn. -red or orange, pink-yellow or black spherical, fleshy pulp in diameter 8-10 mm, seeds 3-4 (sometimes 5) 1 seed each. Flowers in May-June, fruits in September-It ripens in October. The plant blooms profusely, but declines very quickly, sometimes in 2-3 days, especially in hot weather. The plant grows slowly from seed, begins to bear fruit at the age of 10-15 years. The lifespan is up to 400 years. Propagated by seeds, root suckers, cuttings. This type of hawthorn is distributed in the European part of the CIS, Western Siberia and Kazakhstan. . The blood-red hawthorn species belongs to the EUROPEAN SIBERIA species.

because of the presence of thorns, it has been hung on doors since ancient times to protect man from evil spirits that send disease.

In ancient times, the hawthorn tree was considered a tree of winter and darkness for the Celtic peoples, and in Moldova it was a symbol of evil. 372-287 BC). Later, in the first century AD, in the works of Dioscorides, information about the plant was found. Hawthorn appeared in European scientific medicine in the 19th century. Some doctors at the time believed it to be the most valuable discovery because it was considered a cure for other heart diseases. considered a novelty for modern patients and physicians.

Medicinal properties: In this species of hawthorn, its flowers and fruits are collected as medicinal raw materials. The flowers of this type of flower are not collected together, because the process of building this type of flower slows down and when they dry, their color changes, that is, they turn brown. The dried product is harvested. dried no later than an hour, spread in thin layers between the awnings in tents up to 40 * C in tents or in well-ventilated rooms, and from time to time they are overturned. The shelf life of flowers is -2 years. and has a bitter-tasting taste. The harvest period of the fruit is from the end of September to the ripening period until ripe. Ripe fruits are collected in bags or baskets. The fruits are dried in the sun or in dryers at a temperature of 70 * C. Shelf life is 8 years if the fruit is well dried and stored in a safe place for all students. The dried raw material sometimes opens a pale flower (crystallized sugar).

Preparations made from hawthorn fruit improve heart function, prevent early fatigue, which is why it is valued in medicine. In addition, it prevents heart rhythm disorders or is useful in the treatment of kisses. This effect is due to the presence of triterpene compounds in the plant and flavanoids. Hawthorn juice calms the central nervous system, improves blood flow. It lowers blood pressure, improves the general condition of the body, increases the appetite in the weakened body. It normalizes sleep and general condition, helps to recover from serious illness and lowers blood cholesterol levels. The liquid extract "Cardiovalena" is part of a complex drug. In folk medicine, blood-red hawthorn is used as an antipyretic, as well as for diarrhea.

Flowers Infusion juice in folk medicine - for insomnia, hypertension - menopause.

Tincture for cardioneurosis, hypertension.

Flowers, fruits. Juice in esophageal neuroses, skin, liver and biliary tract diseases, functional disorders of the heart, angioedema, arterial fibrillation, dizziness, shortness of breath, insomnia, menopause.

The fruit is used in folk medicine for infusion hypertension, vegetative neuroses, dizziness, suffocation in menopause. Some of the substances in it are non-toxic and can be used for a long time, although it is necessary to adhere to a certain dose. Large doses of tincture (100 drops of tincture and more) are considered to relax the movement and slow down the central nervous system. The HAWTHORN substance in hawthorn is very beneficial and is able to regulate diabetes and blood sugar levels. It is also an effective remedy for gastritis. Hawthorn fruit contains a lot of vitamin C and other substances, which have a positive effect on brain function, clarify the mind, improve memory. In TIBET medicine, hawthorn is a treatment for liver and biliary tract diseases widely used.

How to make tinctures and decoctions of hawthorn in various diseases

For use in functional disorders of the heart: Preparation of tincture of hawthorn berries: mix 1 part of crushed hawthorn berries and 10 parts of 70% alcohol and leave for 15 days. Squeeze, squeeze and take 3 times, 30-40 drops for functional disorders of the heart.

For rheumatism: infusions of flowers and fruits: Part 2 For flowers 10 parts of alcohol is mixed, left for a week, 45-40 drops 3 times a day after meals.

Infusion of hawthorn flower; 600ml boiled water 50gr flower, cook for 30 minutes, then remove, consume 200 ml 3 times a day for hypertension, dizziness, palpitations. Another method is to soak 25 grams of fruit in 200 ml of boiling water in a thermos for 4 hours and then weigh, this type of tincture is used in hypertension, general weakness insomnia and drink 50 ml 3-4 times a day before meals.

Hawthorn flower tincture: 1 part of the flower is mixed together with 2 parts of 90% spit, then stored for 15 days and squeezed, and a teaspoon of 30-40 drops is consumed 3 times.

In folk medicine, the fruit of the hawthorn plant is a means of lowering blood pressure: hawthorn berries (4 parts), grass (4 parts), dried grass (4 parts) and ramashka (1 part) mixture is used. To prepare the infusion, pour 1 tablespoon of the mixture and 1 cup of boiling water and insist 1 hour, take 1 tablespoon 3 times daily before meals.

You can also make hawthorn tea. This tea is made from the flowers or fruits of the hawthorn. 1 tablespoons of the flowers or fruit are first shaken with boiling water and then infused with boiled water in the form of tea. Drinking half a cup of this tea 3 times a day lowers blood pressure, eliminates insomnia, calms.

Contraindications to the use of hawthorn

Hawthorn plants and medicines should be consumed in accordance with the instructions and under the advice and supervision of a doctor, as overdose of hawthorn and its drugs can adversely affect human health, as well as disrupt the functioning of human organs. Overdose and irregular drinking can also cause nausea, dizziness, vomiting, and irregular heartbeat. Especially in people with heart disease, such negative consequences can end badly. It is recommended not to eat hawthorn berries or other berries while drinking their tincture. For people with low blood pressure, the consumption of hawthorn berries and juices should be strictly regulated. Hawthorn berries should also be used with caution during pregnancy and lactation.

In nature, all plants are medicinal, albeit to a certain extent. The hawthorn plant is also a cure for many diseases. However, it is possible to use everything in moderation, including the above-mentioned areas of hawthorn distribution and biology, chemical composition, use, use in folk medicine, recipes and standards for the use of drugs derived from it we have received information about the exceptions. The hawthorn plant is used in nature not only in pharmaceuticals, but also in the food industry, where it is used to make jams, jellies, canned sauces, compotes, fruit drinks and more.

Hawthorn flowers — KRATEGI OF PHYSICS

The fruit of the hawthorn is FRUCTUS KRATEGI

Hawthorn - CRATAEGUS OXYACANTHA L

Round blood-red hawthorn - CRATAEGUS SANGUINEA PAL

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